

**The clinical efficacy of hyaluronic acid in the treatment of
peri-implantitis: a systematic review.**

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Declaration of authorship

I, Raid Khayat, hereby confirm that this thesis “The clinical efficacy of hyaluronic acid in the treatment of peri-implantitis: a systematic review.” is original, my own work, and the result of my research. All the sources have been referenced and this thesis has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Raid Khayat". The signature is stylized with a large initial 'R' and a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Abstract

Background: Hyaluronic acid (HA) is naturally synthesized in the body as a large glycosaminoglycan with roles in hydration, anti-inflammation, regeneration, in addition to cell migration and proliferation. The primary objective of this systematic review was to assess the clinical effectiveness of utilizing HA in the treatment of peri-implantitis on the basis of evidence from clinical studies, including comparisons to placebo or active comparators and observations of clinical interventions.

Methods: In accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines, a comprehensive search was conducted across five databases at two different time points to identify randomized and non-randomized controlled trials. Data from six included studies were extracted and analyzed, and then using the Cochrane RoB 2, ROBINS-I, and JBI tools risk of bias was evaluated. The certainty of evidence for key outcomes was graded with the GRADE approach.

Results: The review analyzed six studies with follow-up periods ranging from 15 days to 12 months. The findings were heterogeneous. While some studies demonstrated statistically significant improvements in probing pocket depth (PPD) and bleeding on probing (BOP) with adjunctive HA, other studies reported no significant difference compared to controls. Marginal bone loss (MBL) outcomes were particularly inconsistent. The review found that HA had an anti-inflammatory effect by reducing IL-1 β levels and showed some benefits against the peri-implantitis associated bacterial community.

Conclusion: On the basis of the current evidence, adjunctive HA shows promising effects on clinical parameters such as PPD and BOP and may have a benefit in decreasing levels of early-colonizing bacteria. However, the high degree of heterogeneity in study design, HA formulations, and treatment protocols, coupled with a high risk of bias in many of the included papers, makes it impossible to draw a definitive conclusion. The certainty of evidence for MBL was very low. Subsequent research with standardized, long-term, and well-designed clinical trials is necessary to fully determine HA's role in treating peri-implantitis.

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List of Abbreviations

2D: Two-dimensional

3D: Three-dimensional

ADI: Association of Dental Implantology

BOP: Bleeding on probing

CAL: Clinical attachment loss

CD44: Cluster of Differentiation 44

CD168: Cluster of Differentiation 168

CHX: Chlorhexidine

CI: Confidence interval

Cochrane RoB 2: Cochrane Risk of Bias tool, version 2

GAGs: Glycosaminoglycans

GlcA: Glucuronic acid

GlcNAc: N-acetyl-D-glucosamine

GRADE: Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

HA: Hyaluronic acid

HAS: HA synthase

HMW-HA: High molecular weight hyaluronic acid

Hyal: Hyaluronidase

IL-1 β : Interleukin 1 beta

ISQ: Implant stability quotient

JBI: The Joanna Briggs Institute

kDa: Kilodalton

MBL: Marginal bone loss

NCT: National Clinical Trial

PPD: Probing pocket depth

PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

RHAMM: Receptor for Hyaluronan-Mediated Motility

rRNA: ribosomal RNA

ROBINS-I: Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies

SRP: Scaling and root planing

SUP: Suppuration

TNF: Tumor necrosis factor

UDP-GlcNAc: UDP-N-acetylglucosamine

UDP-GlcA: UDP-glucuronic acid

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Hyaluronic acid

1.1.1. Discovery

In 1934, a high molecular weight polysaccharide was isolated from the vitreous humor of cow eyes by Karl Meyer and John Palmer (Meyer & Palmer, 1934). They described it as viscous and clear, proposing the name “hyaluronic acid” (HA) which is derived from the terms hyaloid (glass-like) and uronic acid.

1.1.2. Structure and biosynthesis

The simplest form of a sugar molecule is a monosaccharide. Monosaccharides such as glucose, fructose, and galactose have six atoms of carbon, twelve atoms of hydrogen, and six atoms of oxygen ($C_6H_{12}O_6$), but with different structural arrangement. These simple sugar molecules can join together via glycosidic bonds to form larger molecules, disaccharides or polysaccharides. These forms of complex carbohydrates can be classified as homopolysaccharides or heteropolysaccharides; the former is composed of the same type of monosaccharides (e.g., starch, cellulose), whereas the latter is composed of different types of monosaccharide units (e.g., HA, heparin) (Nelson et al., 2013).

1.1.2.1. Glycosaminoglycans

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) are heteropolysaccharides characterized by their unique repeating disaccharide units. Each unit is typically composed of one hexosamine (glucosamine or galactosamine) and another uronic acid (glucuronic acid (GlcA) or iduronic acid) (Zhang et al., 2020).

Glucosamine is a derivative of glucose, in its biosynthesis, glucose is first phosphorylated by the hexokinase enzyme which adds a phosphate group to the C6 position. Phosphorylation is an essential step that regulates metabolism, by making the glucose molecule more reactive, and susceptible to modifications. Second, glucose-6-phosphate is isomerized to fructose-6-phosphate by the phosphoglucose isomerase enzyme (glucose-6-phosphate isomerase). Isomerization refers to the rearrangement of a molecule while maintaining the same chemical formula. The glutamine aminotransferase enzyme then utilizes glutamine, the most abundant amino acid in the body, which donates the amino group (NH₂) to be added to the C2 position in the fructose-6-phosphate. This reaction, catalyzed by glucosamine-6-phosphate synthetase, produces glucosamine-6-phosphate and represents the *de novo* pathway of glucosamine synthesis (Paneque et al., 2023).

1.1.2.1.1. Synthesis of UDP-N-acetylglucosamine

The modification of glucosamine-6-phosphate to N-acetylglucosamine-6-phosphate occurs through acetylation, adding an acetyl group (CH₃CO-) to the existing amino group (-NH₂) by the glucosamine-phosphate N-acetyltransferase 1 enzyme utilizing acetyl-CoA.

The final step in the hexosamine biosynthetic pathway is carried out by the enzyme UDP-N-acetylglucosamine pyrophosphorylase which utilizes uridine triphosphate to produce UDP-N-acetylglucosamine (UDP-GlcNAc) and releases pyrophosphate (Paneque et al., 2023).

1.1.2.1.2. Synthesis of UDP-glucuronic acid

Glucose is a monosaccharide with an aldehyde group (CHO) at the C₁ position. Sugar acids such as gluconic acid, glucaric acid, and GlcA result from oxidation of glucose, which involves adding an oxygen atom to transform the molecule. GlcA is formed by oxidation of the primary alcohol group (CH₂OH) at the C₆ of glucose into a carboxylic acid group (COOH), without affecting the aldehyde group by enzymes such as glucose oxidase (Shendurse & Khedkar, 2016).

In the biosynthetic pathway leading to UDP-glucuronic acid (UDP-GlcA), glucose is first converted to glucose-6-phosphate (G6P) via phosphorylation, followed by its conversion to glucose-1-phosphate (G1P). Subsequently, uridine triphosphate (UTP) interacts with G1P to create UDP-glucose. Finally, the enzyme UDP-glucose dehydrogenase (UGDH) oxidizes UDP-glucose to form UDP-GlcA, completing the classical biosynthetic pathway (Kobayashi et al., 2020).

1.1.3. Chemical composition and properties

HA which is also known as hyaluronan is a specific type of GAG; it is composed of building blocks of N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) joined with GlcA to form the largest polysaccharide in vertebrates including humans. Unlike other shorter GAGs, HA may reach up to 50,000 repeats of disaccharide units (100,000 monosaccharide units) (Hascall V, 2017; Nelson et al., 2013).

These disaccharide units are linked by two types of bonds. The β (1 \rightarrow 3) glycosidic bond link the D-glucuronic acid to the N-acetyl-D-glucosamine within each unit itself, whereas the β (1 \rightarrow 4) glycosidic bonds link the N-acetyl-D-glucosamine to the next D-glucuronic acid in the neighboring disaccharide unit. The 'D' and ' β ' prefixes refer to the stereochemical and anomeric configurations, respectively, whereas the numbers indicate the carbon atoms involved in the bonds (Jiang et al., 2007).

To simplify, HA is a complex carbohydrate composed of repeating and alternating disaccharides made from monosaccharide units of GlcNAc and GlcA (Balagurunathan et al., 2014) (Figure 1). HA is the only GAG that is not sulfated or covalently joined to a core protein rendering it a free existing polysaccharide. These characteristics of HA influence its unique features of hydrating capacity, viscosity, and ability to interact with a wider range of molecules (Mende et al., 2016).

Fig.1. Basic illustration of building blocks of hyaluronic acid. (HAS) hyaluronic acid synthase.

1.1.4. HA synthase enzymes and biosynthesis

The synthesis of HA occurs on the inner surface of the plasma membrane of many cell types by three HA synthase enzymes (HAS). These enzymes utilize UDP-GlcNAc and UDP-GlcA to construct chains of HA. As the chain becomes larger, it is subsequently secreted into the extracellular matrix, and this allows for a large molecule of HA which serves its structural and regulatory functions. HAS1, HAS2, and HAS3 are differently expressed in various tissues and have been shown to biosynthesize HA at variable sizes which in turn influence its functions (Itano et al., 1999; Salih et al., 2024; Weigel et al., 1997).

The least active HAS1 primarily synthesizes medium to high molecular weight HA (HMW-HA) (200–2000 kDa). HAS2 synthesizes HMW-HA (>2000 kDa), while it is more active and often is associated with regeneration and healing. Low molecular weight HA (\approx 200 kDa) is made by HAS3, which is the most active (Kalia & Avérous, 2011; Mende et al., 2016). HA is mostly synthesized as a HMW-HA polymer with an average size between 1000–8000 kDa (Cowman et al., 2015a), however its mass differs on the basis of many factors such as the tissue type, function, and metabolic activity. For comparison, other GAGs do not exceed 50 kDa on average (Kalia & Avérous, 2011).

1.1.5. Physical and biochemical properties

HA is a viscous polymer with a molecular mass ranging from a few hundred to 8000 kDa. High viscosity is correlated with many factors including high concentration, molecular mass, and flexibility of its chains. Moreover, its water-interaction unique property enables it to form a large hydration shell increasing its overall size, constantly altering its shape, and contributing to its viscosity. As the HA polymer expands, it occupies more space, rendering additional ability to interact with greater amounts of both bounded and unbounded water molecules at a faster rate which further increases its hydrodynamic volume. This exponential increase in size relative to mass is approximately calculated to the power of 1.8. As the hydrodynamic sphere continues to grow, the gross density of the HA polymer becomes lower, however, its concentration remains highest near the center (Cowman et al., 2015a; Cowman & Matsuoka, 2005; Cowman et al., 2015b).

1.1.6. Distribution, receptors, and degradation

The skin contains 50% of the total content of HA in the body, with the majority found in the dermis, particularly the papillary dermis. Interestingly, as people age, the HA content in the epidermis significantly decreases while remaining relatively lasting in the dermis (Meyer & Stern, 1994; Papakonstantinou et al., 2012). The connective tissues of the muscles and umbilical cord also contain high concentrations of HA (Necas et al., 2008). In addition, HMW-HA is a major component of the synovial fluid in the knee (approximately 2–3 mg/ml), and has significant contribution in its viscosity aiding lubrication of the joint (Balazs et al., 1967; Cowman et al., 2015b; Kalia & Avérous, 2011). In vertebrates, the amount of HA varies across the extracellular matrix of most tissues, with a total average of 15 g in the body (Stern, 2004).

HA primarily binds to the cell surface receptor Cluster of Differentiation 44 (CD44), which is found on most cell types, and to the Cluster of Differentiation 168 (CD168), also known as RHAMM (Receptor for Hyaluronan-Mediated Motility) in variable distributions and expressions (Aruffo et al., 1990; Kouvidi et al., 2011; Papakonstantinou et al., 2012).

In general, HA has a fast turnover; a process essential for tissue repair. In the anterior chamber of the eye, it is 1–2 hours; less than 1 day in the joints; and between 2–5 days in the skin. However, it has a longer half-life in the vitreous body that ranges between 20–70 days (Kalia & Avérous, 2011). About 30% of HA degrades and replenishes in the body everyday (Mende et al., 2016; Stern, 2004).

HA undergoes degradation through two main pathways, the first is carried out by the action of hyaluronidase (Hyal), while the other is a non-specific process involving damage to HA caused by oxygen radicals (Salih et al., 2024).

1.1.7. Key functions and biological effects

HA has the capacity to bind up to 1000 times its weight in water due to its polyanionic properties, which makes it highly hydrophilic and retentive to water molecules. This aids in hydration, lubrication, and structural support. Viscous gel-like HA can act as a shock absorbent by filling dead spaces (Kalia & Avérous, 2011; Ucm et al., 2022).

At the cellular level, HA provides a structural hydrated matrix that facilitates cell migration and free movement as observed in HA-rich early granulation tissue. Furthermore, HA has a key role in wound healing and tissue regeneration. It creates a moist environment that acts as a physical scaffold, modulates inflammation, and is conducive for cell migration and proliferation. It has also been found that low molecular weight HA products stimulate pro-inflammatory responses by upregulating cytokines, while HMW-HA suppresses the inflammation (anti-inflammatory effect). Other properties also include angiogenesis, bacteriostatic effect, and non-antigenicity, since it is naturally occurring, it does not provoke an immune response (Chen & Abatangelo, 1999; Deepika Ajit Masurkar, 2023; Litwiniuk et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2021).

1.1.8. Hyaluronidase enzymes

Hyal is the enzyme that breaks down HA. Three main categories of Hyals were described by Meyer based on their origin and mode of action. This first type was referred to as the Testicular-type Hyal, which was primarily derived from the spermatozoa of the mammalian testes, with mature bulls as a major source. This type of Hyal has been isolated from other sources including rat liver lysosomes and submandibular glands of canines, in addition to the venom of bees and some snakes.

The second type is the Bacterial Hyal that was produced by various bacteria, including *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Clostridium*, *Clostridium welchii*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Flavobacterium*. This microbial Hyal is an endo- β -N-acetyl-hexosaminidase similar to the testicular-type enzyme. However, the testicular-type Hyal breaks HA bonds between GlcNAc and GlcA through hydrolysis whereas the microbial Hyal lyses the bond through β -elimination.

The third type, Leech Hyal (*Hirudo medicinalis*), is isolated from the salivary glands of leeches. It is an endo- β -glucuronidase enzyme that cleaves the endo- β -glucuronidic bonds (Meyer, 1971).

Humans have six genes that create Hyal-like enzymes clustered on two chromosomes. Chromosome 3p21.3 contains Hyal-1, Hyal-2, and Hyal-3 whereas chromosome 7q31.3 contains Hyal-4, PH-20, and HYALP1.

Human Hyal-1 and Hyal-2 are the main enzymes to degrade HA in body tissues. Human Hyal-1 breaks down HMW-HA into tetrasaccharides and is present in several organs, including the liver, kidneys, spleen, and heart, as well as in plasma, serum, and urine. Human Hyal-2 has a lower activity than Hyal-1 and it breaks down HMW-HA into approximately 20 kDa units. The functions of Hyal-3 and Hyal-4 are unclear. However, the former is found to be highly expressed in the bone marrow and testes, while the latter is found in skeletal muscle and the placenta (Csoka et al., 2001).

PH-20 is a testicular enzyme encoded by the Spam1 gene (sperm adhesion molecule 1). Its presence is essential in the human sperm to hydrolyze the HA on the oocyte surface, in order to facilitate fertilization. Its presence was also reported in the female reproductive system, suggesting possible additional functions (Csoka et al., 2001; Stern & Jedrzejewski, 2006).

Finally, HYALP1 is a pseudogene defined by two deletions that disrupt its coding sequence and production of Hyal activity. However, in mice and other mammals, it retains its integrity and is able to encode an active Hyal (Csoka et al., 2001). Hyals mainly hydrolyze the $\beta(1\rightarrow4)$ bonds between the disaccharide units in HA (Jiang et al., 2007).

1.1.9. HA production and modification

Efforts to meet the increasing demand for HA have led to the development of efficient production methods. The diverse and distinctive applications of HA necessitate high purity and economical products. Animal-derived HA has been substituted by microbially fermented HA, which has an immense supply of raw material, consistent quality, and reduced contamination. *Streptococcus* species, particularly *Streptococcus equi* subsp. *zooepidemicus*, are being utilized to produce clinically suitable HMW-HA (Rangaswamy & Jain, 2008; Schanté et al., 2011; Ucm et al., 2022).

To enhance the properties of HA, it can be chemically modified to produce new materials. This can be accomplished via two main methods: cross-linking and conjugation. Cross-linking refers to interconnecting multiple different HA chains together using two or more chemical bonds, increasing molecular weight and viscosity. The process of cross-linking can be carried out by different techniques including direct cross-linking with added agents such as 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether or cross-linking with HA derivatives. Conjugation refers to coupling a compound such as a drug or a growth factor to HA using a single bond. As HA penetrates the desired target site, this bond breaks and the compound is released. This can enhance drug delivery as in injecting ibuprofen or hydrocortisone attached to HA in joints (Schanté et al., 2011). Injected linear HA degrades fast, and cross-linking stabilizes the product to provide longevity and viscosity. Cross-linked hydrogels have shown better penetration of human and animal skin when compared to linear HA (Berkó et al., 2013).

Cross-linked HA follows the same degradation pathway as linear HA. Traces of 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether, used as a cross-linking agent in HA, have been shown to be harmless (<2 ppm) (De Boule et al., 2013).

HA is not limited to extensive use in aesthetics; it is also employed in oculoplastic surgeries, musculoskeletal disorders, drug delivery, and many other applications (Ucm et al., 2022). Given its diverse properties, the use of HA within the oral cavity has also been a topic of interest.

1.2. Dental implants

1.2.1. Role of HA in periodontal health

The most abundant cell type of the gingival connective tissue are fibroblasts, which have an essential role in wound healing. In a study on harvested human gingival cells, two different types of HA were used, non-cross-linked and cross-linked formulations, both with different molecular weights. They were found to be biocompatible in addition to having strong proliferative and migratory functions. Fibroblast migration has increased six- to nine-fold in the presence of exogenous HA compared to controls (Asparuhova et al., 2019).

Moreover, these formulations of HA were found to have a strong influence on osteoprogenitor cell growth, demonstrating an important role in both the soft and hard tissues of the periodontium (Asparuhova et al., 2020).

In an animal study Shirakata et al., have surgically created two-wall intrabony defects in healthy dogs to investigate the effects of HA alone or in combination with a collagen matrix on periodontal regeneration. Histological evaluation confirmed the formation of new bone and cementum in both treatment groups, demonstrating the role of HA as a therapeutic agent in periodontal regeneration. Similarly, researchers have explored the treatment of surgically induced class III furcation defects using HA alone or in conjunction with a collagen matrix. Both approaches showed new connective tissue attachment, as confirmed by histological analysis. The two studies reported statistical significance when compared to open flap debridement alone (Shirakata et al., 2021; Shirakata et al., 2022).

Furthermore, studies on periodontal tissue repair using HA gels in humans demonstrated a role in collagen turnover in wound healing (Pilloni et al., 2023; Vela et al., 2024b). Moreover, subgingival application of 0.8% of HA gel (GENGIGEL®) combined with scaling and root planing (SRP), has been reported to have an overall positive effect in treating moderate to severe chronic periodontitis compared to SRP alone in a human split-mouth study (Al-Shammari et al., 2018).

A clinical trial was conducted to compare the use of cross-linked HA (hyaDENT BG®) in combination with open flap debridement versus open flap debridement alone for the treatment of suprabony defects. The clinical parameters in these patients have improved significantly in the treatment group (Vela et al., 2024a).

In addition to improvement in clinical measures, microbial reduction, namely *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* and *Porphyromonas gingivalis* was reported when SRP was combined with HA gel (GENGIGEL®) in both smokers and non-smokers with chronic periodontitis in a split-mouth study design. The effect of HA on pathogens was attributed to its ability to influence the migration of polymorphonuclear leukocytes and macrophages (Vajawat et al., 2022).

1.2.2. Peri-implant diseases

Missing teeth can be replaced with fixed bridges, removable prostheses, or dental implants. While each of these options has its advantages and disadvantages, dental implants are considered the gold standard because of their ability to replicate natural teeth in terms of function, aesthetics, and longevity. However, implants are still prone to peri-implant diseases that affect their success and survival in the mouth.

In 1965, Levignac described osteolysis around implants as “*périimplantose*” (Levignac, 1965). Subsequent research into inflammation, pocket depth, and the presence of specific bacteria, with or without bone loss, has contributed to the criteria for describing implant success, peri-implant health, and associated peri-implant diseases.

In 1993, the terms peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis became the standard terms describing two distinct conditions, where the former involves the surrounding soft tissue without involvement of the bone. Other conditions that may also affect dental implants include retrograde peri-implantitis and peri-implant abscess (Atieh & Alsabeeha, 2024).

1.2.2.1. Peri-implant mucositis

According to *The 2017 World Workshop on the Classification of Periodontal and Peri-Implant Diseases and Conditions*, characteristics of peri-implant mucositis primarily include bleeding on probing (BOP), with or without the presence of erythema, swelling, and suppuration (SUP). Plaque plays a central pathological role in peri-implant mucositis based on experimental human and animal studies (Berglundh et al., 2018).

1.2.2.2. Peri-implantitis

Peri-implantitis represents the progression of peri-implant mucositis that includes the clinical signs of inflammation but marked by bone loss. Plaque is also implicated, as supported by evidence from observational studies. Increased probing depth coupled with inflammation and progressive bone loss reflect the severity of the disease. The lesion extends apically beyond the junctional epithelium with increased numbers of white blood cells namely plasma cells, macrophages, and neutrophils. Probing depth of ≥ 6 mm and coronal bone loss of the intraosseous implant of ≥ 3 mm serve as clinical diagnostics. While bone remodeling is expected after implant insertion, pathological bone loss extends beyond normal changes. Diagnosis is aided by comparison to previous examinations; if unavailable, bone levels of ≥ 3 mm apical to the implant's most coronal intra-osseous portion, combined with BOP, are consistent with a peri-implantitis diagnosis. The absence of erythema, BOP, swelling, and SUP is indicative of healthy peri-implant tissues. Defining a precise probing depth range that corresponds to health is not feasible, as peri-implant health can still be present with reduced bone support (Berglundh et al., 2018).

1.2.3. Treatment approach for peri-implantitis

If the implant is considered failed, it may be left in situ or, more commonly, removed, with or without restorative plans, depending on the patient's autonomy and the clinical situation. Standardized guidelines are not yet fully established but, when implants have a potentially positive prognosis, treatment decisions for peri-implantitis are directed toward stopping disease progression and this involves surgical or non-surgical approaches.

Non-surgical treatment, such as mechanical debridement alone, is generally considered insufficient, however, the addition of adjunctive antimicrobials may lead to better outcomes. Surgical approaches include access flap for improved visualization, debridement, and local delivery of drugs. Moreover, resection of the pathological pockets and regeneration of bony defects may also be considered. A reduced probing depth and the absence of bleeding on probing, with no further bone loss are crucial signs of disease remission. The goal is to stop the progression of the disease and to improve prognosis. The disease requires ongoing management, including regular maintenance and re-evaluation along with the patient's compliance, to prevent recurrence and improve survival rates (Hong et al., 2024). Decision-making regarding the treatment of peri-implantitis varies among clinicians and is still evolving to seek universal standards (Dell'Olmo et al., 2022; Paula et al., 2024).

1.3. Research question, objectives, and aims

Does the use of hyaluronic acid improve clinical and radiographic outcomes in the treatment of peri-implantitis?

The broad objectives of this thesis are to provide a comprehensive understanding of hyaluronic acid, including its biosynthesis and biological properties as well as to describe peri-implantitis and critically evaluate the existing clinical evidence utilizing hyaluronic acid in its management.

The specific aims of the systematic review are to:

- Systematically search for and identify studies on the use of hyaluronic acid for the treatment of peri-implantitis.
- Evaluate their clinical and radiographic outcomes.
- Assess the risk of bias and quality of evidence of the included studies.

Chapter 2: Materials and methods

2.1. Review protocol

This systematic review was conducted and reported in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 statement and a PRISMA flow diagram was used to document the study selection process. The protocol for this systematic review was registered with the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) on 09 March 2025 (Registration ID: CRD420251007717). The protocol can be accessed at: <https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO/view/CRD420251007717>

2.2. Research question (PICO format)

Problem (P): Patients diagnosed with peri-implantitis. **Intervention (I):** Treatment involving the use of hyaluronic acid as an adjunct to non-surgical or surgical therapy. **Control (C):** Placebo, no additional treatment, or active comparators. **Outcome (O):** Changes in clinical parameters (probing pocket depth, bleeding on probing, suppuration, clinical attachment level, radiographic bone level change) and other relevant outcomes (e.g., biomarkers, adverse events).

2.3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

English-language publications of randomized controlled trials and non-randomized controlled trials that utilized HA in the treatment of peri-implantitis were included without a restricted time frame on publication dates.

2.3.1. Exclusion criteria

- Studies reporting the use of HA as a preventative measure for peri-implantitis or for the maintenance of dental implants.
- Studies reporting on the treatment of peri-mucositis or deficient soft tissue only.
- Studies that do not utilize HA in the treatment of peri-implantitis.
- Studies conducted in vitro or on animals.
- Reviews, case reports, editorials, conference abstracts, and opinion pieces.

2.4. Search strategy

The search was initially conducted in September 2024 and repeated in February 2025 across the following databases: PubMed, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, Embase, Web of Science, and Scopus.

2.4.1. Search terms

The search was conducted using a combination of the following main search terms: peri-implantitis and hyaluronic acid. The exact search strategy was tailored for each database to optimize the results, with the core terms being (("Hyaluronic Acid" OR "Hyaluronan") AND ("Peri-implantitis" OR "Periimplantitis" OR "Peri-implant" OR "Dental implant"))).

2.5. Data collection and analysis

The titles and abstracts of the identified studies were screened by the author on the basis of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Then, full-text articles of potentially eligible studies were assessed against the inclusion criteria, and reasons for exclusion were documented at this stage.

2.6. Data extraction

The extracted data included study characteristics, participant demographics, peri-implantitis diagnosis criteria, HA specifications, details of the intervention, outcome measures, and results.

2.7. Assessment of risk of bias

The Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 (RoB 2) tool was used to evaluate RCTs. The controlled pilot study with a split-mouth design was assessed using The Risk of Bias in Non-Randomized Studies (ROBINS-1) tool. The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) tool was used for the case series study (Munn et al., 2020).

2.8. Assessment of certainty of evidence

The certainty of evidence for the main outcomes was assessed using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach.

2.9. Outcomes to be analyzed

2.9.1 Main outcomes

- Changes in probing pocket depth
- Change in bleeding on probing
- Changes in suppuration
- Radiographic bone level changes
- Changes in clinical attachment level

2.9.2. Additional outcomes

- Biomarkers
- Adverse events

Chapter 3: Results

This review included six published papers: four RCTs, one controlled pilot study with a split-mouth design, and one case series. The most recent study was published in 2024, while the earliest was published in 2009. No published English studies meeting the inclusion criteria were found between 2009 and the next consecutive included study in 2017. All included studies were conducted in Europe: Spain (n=2), Serbia (n=1), Portugal (n=1), Italy (n=1), and Germany (n=1) (Table 1). The study selection process, including the number of articles identified, screened, and ultimately included in the review, is visually summarized in the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 2). Reasons for exclusion include studies that were not published in English, trial registry records of unpublished data, trial registry records of reports that were included under a different title, a conference abstract, and studies with different focus such as prevention or unrelated clinical problems.

3.1. Sample size

The total sample sizes ranged from 5 to 63 patients (Table 2). The studies investigated the use of HA as a non-surgical or surgical adjunct for the treatment of peri-implantitis, with follow-up periods ranging from 15 days to 12 months. Two publications (Soriano-Lerma et al., 2020; Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021) reported different outcomes from the same patient cohort within a single clinical trial registry (NCT03157193). Their outcomes were analyzed separately without double-counting the sample size.

Table 1: RCTs and non-RCTs included in the systematic review.

Study	Author/ Year / Country	Journal	DOI / PMID
Hyaluronic acid reduces inflammation and crevicular fluid IL-1β concentrations in peri-implantitis: a randomized controlled clinical trial	(Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021) Spain	Journal of Periodontal and Implant Science	https://doi.org/10.5051/jpis.1903660183
Reconstructive peri-Implantitis therapy by using bovine bone substitute with or without hyaluronic acid: a randomized clinical controlled pilot study	(Rakašević et al., 2023) Serbia	Journal of Functional Biomaterials	https://doi.org/10.3390/jfb14030149
Short-term effects of hyaluronic acid on the subgingival microbiome in peri-implantitis: A randomized controlled clinical trial	(Soriano-Lerma et al., 2020) Spain	Journal of Periodontology	https://doi.org/10.1002/jper.19-0184
Non-surgical treatment of peri-implant pockets: an exploratory study comparing 0.2% chlorhexidine and 0.8% hyaluronic acid	(De Araújo Nobre et al., 2009) Portugal	Canadian journal of dental hygiene	https://www.cochranelibrary.com/central/doi/10.1002/central/CN-01051284/full
The use of hyaluronic acid as an adjuvant in the management of peri-implantitis	(Lopez et al., 2017) Italy	Journal of Biological Regulators and Homeostatic Agents	PMID: 29202572
Reconstructive surgical therapy of peri-implant defects with ribose cross-linked collagen matrix and crosslinked hyaluronic acid - a prospective case series	(Friedmann et al., 2024) Germany	Clinical Oral Investigations	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-024-05942-6

Figure 2: PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

This figure illustrates the flow of studies identified, screened, and included in the systematic review on HA for the treatment of peri-implantitis.

Table 2: Sample size summary. T= test, C1= control group 1 (placebo), C2 = control group 2 (no treatment), HA group (treated with hyaluronic acid), CHX group (treated with chlorhexidine).

Study	Sample size (patients)	Sample size (implants)	Age (mean \pm SD)	Lost to follow up/discontinued
Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021	61	100 (32T, 32C1, 36C2)	Test: 60 \pm 9 (n=21); C1: 64 \pm 7 (n=20); C2: 58 \pm 13 (n=20)	Initially, 63 patients; 2 lost to follow-up
Rakašević et al., 2023	13	19	46.85 \pm 9.96	Test n=6/ C n=7; 0 lost to follow up
Soriano-Lerma et al., 2020	54	108 samples from 104 implants (38T, 34C1, 36C2)	Test: 60 \pm 9 (n=21); C1: 64 \pm 6 (n=21); C2: 58 \pm 12 (n=21)	Initially, 63 patients; 2 lost to follow-up/ For 9 patients, no DNA amplification was achieved
De Araújo Nobre et al., 2009	18	18 (HA group n=9, CHX group n=9)	HA group: 56.2 \pm 1.7; CHX group: 58.7 \pm 3.1	6 patients (5 non-compliant, 1 death; unrelated) before the 1-year follow-up
M. A. Lopez et al., 2017	5	Not specified; at least one implant in different hemi-arches	Not reported	0 lost to follow up
Friedmann et al., 2024	13	15	64.3 \pm 9.75	0 lost to follow up

3.2. Diagnosis of peri-implantitis

The diagnosis of peri-implantitis varied across studies. **Sánchez-Fernández et al.** and **Soriano-Lerma et al.** applied *the Association of Dental Implantology (ADI)* criteria that included PPD of ≥ 4 mm, BOP, and MBL > 2 mm. **Rakašević et al.** applied *the 2017 World Workshop Consensus*. **De Araújo Nobre et al.** defined the disease by PPD of ≥ 5 mm, BOP, and bone loss between the coronal and middle 3rd of the implant. **Lopez et al.** demarcated the presence of PPD between 4 and 7 mm, spontaneous bleeding, or BOP. PPD of ≥ 6 mm and radiographic peri-implant bone loss below the implant shoulder were set by **Friedmann et al.**

3.3. Protocols for HA

HA was used in various protocols, either combined with non-surgical treatment (as a topical gel and for intra-pocket irrigation) or with surgical reconstruction (in which it was directly applied to defects, implant surfaces, and the matrix, or supplied as pre-mixed bone substitutes) (Table 3).

Table 3: HA use specifications, post-operative instructions, and follow-up periods. All patients have received non-surgical periodontal therapy. (G1) group 1, (G2) group 2, (HA) hyaluronic acid, (CHX) chlorhexidine.

Study	Type of HA	Was the prosthesis removed?	Comparator	Protocol	Post-operative instructions	Follow up period
Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021	0.8% HMW-HA gel (crosslinked HA, 6–7×106 Da, Ricerfarma srl) and 0.2% HA gel	No	G1: Placebo G2: No treatment	Application in the peri-implant pocket once in the clinic then 3 times per day at home for 45 days	Home application was to be performed by massaging the gingiva around the affected area after toothbrushing, followed by avoiding eating or drinking for 20 minutes afterward.	45 days and 90 days
Rakašević et al., 2023	(Cerabone® plus, Botiss Biomaterials GmbH, Berlin, Germany)	Yes, 2 weeks before the surgical intervention	Bovine bone substitute without HA	Surgical reconstruction using a pre-mixed bovine bone substitute with HA	Amoxicillin (500 mg, 3 times/day) or Clindamycin (600 mg, 3 times/day) for 5 days. To avoid brushing for 3 weeks and to use chlorhexidine 0.12% twice daily for 14 days. For a period of three months, patients received bi-weekly professional dental hygiene to the treated area.	6 months
Soriano-Lerma et al., 2020	0.8% HMW-HA gel (crosslinked HA, 6–7×106 Da, Ricerfarma srl) and 0.2% HA gel	No	G1: Placebo G2: No treatment	Application in the peri-implant pocket once in the clinic then 3 times per day at home for 45 days	Home application was to be performed by massaging the gingiva around the affected area after toothbrushing, followed by avoiding eating or drinking for 20 minutes afterward.	45 days
De Araújo Nobre et al., 2009	HA 0.8% gel (Gengigel®, Ricerfarma, Milano, Italy)	Yes, as shown on figures.	CHX 0.2% gel	In-office irrigation of peri-implant pockets, then brushing at home using gel	To avoid eating, drinking, or rinsing for at least half an hour after office treatment. To use a soft toothbrush and to apply either a 0.2% CHX gel or a 0.2% HA gel (Frequency and duration were not mentioned).	1 month then 1 year

Study	Type of HA	Was the prosthesis removed?	Comparator	Protocol	Post-operative instructions	Follow up period
M. A. Lopez et al., 2017	(IBSA Farmaceutici Italia Srl, Lodi, Italy)	Not reported	Split-mouth design- no gel	Nebulized via spray once in the clinic then twice per day at home for 15 days	To perform two self-administrations of nebulized HA per day for 15 days on the treated side.	15 days
Friedmann et al., 2024	1.4-butanediol diglycidyl ether (BDDE)-crosslinked hyaluronic acid gel (xHyA, HyaDENT BG®, Regedent AG, Switzerland (1.6% cross-linked hyaluronic acid, 0.2% natural hyaluronic acid)	No	None	Surgical reconstruction with ribose cross-linked collagen matrix and application of HA on the defect walls, implant surfaces, and the matrix.	To avoid mechanical oral hygiene measures for 6 weeks with the implementation of a chlorhexidine protocol. Doxycycline 200 mg, once/day for 10 days. Ibuprofen, if needed.	Weekly during the initial 6 weeks post-op Quarterly periodontal therapy Assessments at 12 weeks Outcomes measured at the 12 months

3.4. Main outcomes

3.4.1. Probing pocket depth and clinical attachment loss

Sánchez-Fernández et al.: There was a statistically significant reduction in PPD in the test group in comparison with the control group 1 at 45 and 90 days ($p < 0.01$). CAL was reduced but without statistical significance in any group. **Rakašević et al.:** Baseline means for the HA and control groups were 5.38 ± 1.06 mm and 5.10 ± 0.92 mm respectively. PPD at 6 months was 2.34 ± 0.4 mm for the HA group and 2.51 ± 0.39 mm for the control group. Although both groups showed improvements in PPD and CAL over time, no statistically significant differences were observed between the study groups.

De Araújo Nobre et al.: The mean PPD scores were 5.6 mm and 5.7 mm for the HA and chlorhexidine (CHX) groups respectively. At one-month post-treatment, mean scores were 4.4 mm and 4.1 mm in the same order. Both the HA and CHX groups showed statistically significant improvements ($p = 0.031$ and $p = 0.008$) in PPD from baseline within their respective groups. Attachment level showed statistical significance in both groups ($p < 0.05$). At the one-year follow-up, the overall means of PPD and attachment level were 3.3 mm and 2.6 mm, respectively. However, there was no significant difference between the two groups. **Lopez et al.:** There was a lack of numerical data and results were descriptive. A slight, statistically irrelevant difference in pocket depth was reported between the HA and control sides at 15 days post-treatment.

Friedmann et al.: There was a statistically significant PPD reduction at 12 months, 3.2 ± 0.66 mm compared to the baseline 7.2 ± 1.9 mm ($p < 0.0001$). There was also a statistically significant increase in buccal soft tissue dehiscence from 0.56 ± 1.22 mm at baseline to 2.43 ± 0.93 mm at 12 months ($p < 0.0001$). However, attachment levels were described to be comparable to those in the literature.

3.4.2. Bleeding on probing

Sánchez-Fernández et al.: All implants had BOP at baseline. The HA group showed the greatest reduction in BOP in both the 45-day and the 90-day follow-up, with a borderline significance when compared to the no-product control group at 90 days ($p = 0.07$). **Rakašević et al.:** The HA group showed a complete resolution in BOP at 6 months, while the control group still had a mean score of 0.17 ± 0.39 ; however, without statistical significance.

De Araújo Nobre et al.: The mean modified Bleeding Index scores were 2.2 and 1.9 for the HA and CHX groups respectively. At one-month post-treatment, mean scores were 1 and 0.7, respectively. The overall mean of the bleeding index after one year was 0.3. No statistically significant difference in treatment between the two groups.

Lopez et al.: In the five included patients, an improvement in BOP at the 15-day follow-up was described in both the HA-treated and non-HA-treated sites, with no greater improvement observed on the HA side. **Friedmann et al.:** A statistically significant reduction in BOP frequency was observed, dropping from 63% at baseline to 10% of sites at 12 months ($p < 0.001$).

3.4.3. Marginal bone loss / bone gain

Sánchez-Fernández et al.: The MBL baseline in the HA group was 3.41 ± 1.66 mm. It showed a minor numerical decrease to 3.40 ± 1.63 mm at 45 days and 3.39 ± 1.70 mm at 90 days. It increased in the control groups, though none of these differences were statistically significant. MBL was determined using parallel periapical x-rays.

Rakašević et al.: There was a significant bone gain in both groups 6 months after surgery ($p < 0.05$). Statistically greater vertical bone gain was observed in the HA group (mesial, distal, and oral sites) compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). Bone levels were assessed using cone-beam computed tomography.

De Araújo Nobre et al.: Using periapical x-rays, baseline bone loss was described as localized to the middle third in four out of 18 implants, while the other 14 implants had bone loss in the coronal third. Post-treatment bone loss evaluation remained with the same descriptions in both treatment groups of HA and CHX at the 1-month follow-up. The MBL was not evaluated at the 1-year follow-up. **Lopez et al.:** Radiographic assessment of marginal bone loss was not reported in this study.

Friedmann et al.: Baseline MBL was 5.83 ± 2.63 mm, a significant mean of marginal bone gain 1.02 ± 0.64 mm was reported at the 12-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$). MBL was assessed using parallel periapical x-rays.

3.4.4. Microbiome changes

Soriano-Lerma et al.: The primary outcome measured in this study following the use of HA was its effect on the subgingival microbiome. Using 16S rRNA gene sequencing to identify bacteria from peri-implantitis sites, a total of 27 phyla and 604 genera were detected. Fifty-three genera that had a higher relative abundance (more than 0.1%) were analyzed. Pre-treatment samples from peri-implantitis sites were found to have one of three distinct microbial strata.

Stratum 1: characterized by a high relative abundance of the genera *Ralstonia* and *Sphingomonas*.

Stratum 2: characterized by an abundance of *Streptococcus*, *Neisseria*, *Veillonella*, and *Rothia*.

Stratum 3: characterized by the presence of *Fusobacterium*, *Prevotella*, *Porphyromonas*, *Treponema*, *Campylobacter*, and *Tannerella*.

In the test group, post-treatment with the HMW-HA samples at 45 days showed no differences in the low diversity stratum 1. In stratum 2, there was a significant decrease in the levels of *Streptococcus*, *Veillonella*, *Rothia*, and *Granulicatella* ($p < 0.05$). In stratum 3, a significant decrease in the levels of *Prevotella* and *Campylobacter* was found ($p < 0.05$). In samples from control group 1 (placebo) and 2 (no treatment), no variations were found in strata 1 and 2. In stratum 3 of control group 1, levels of *Propionibacterium*, *Neisseria*, *Rothia*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Mycoplasma* had a significant rise ($p < 0.05$), along with a significant reduction in *Anaeroglobulus* ($p < 0.05$).

Stratum 3 in the control group 2 samples showed a significant increase in the levels of *Atopobium* and *Anaeroglobulus* ($p < 0.05$), in addition to a decrease in *Porphyromonas* ($p < 0.05$).

3.5. Additional outcomes

Proinflammatory cytokines in Sánchez-Fernández et al.: Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) and tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) were measured in crevicular fluid samples from peri-implantitis sites at baseline and at 45 days after treatment. A significant reduction in IL-1 β was found in the test subgroup compared with the no treatment group ($p = 0.04$). **Implant stability quotient (ISQ) in Rakašević et al.:** Using Penguin®, ISQ values were measured at different time points. The test group showed statistically significantly higher scores compared to the control group at 3- and 6-months post-treatment ($p = 0.009$ and $p = 0.032$, respectively).

Lopez et al.: reported a 100% resolution in tartar and plaques indices but without statistical significance. **Friedmann et al.:** Radiographic analysis post-surgical treatment revealed a significant reduction of defects with a newly mineralized bone area of $27.65 \pm 18.50 \text{ mm}^2$ ($p < 0.0001$), which translated to a 69.1% gain of mineralized tissue (Table 4).

3.6. Treatment success criteria

Rakašević et al.: Treatment success was defined as the absence of SUP and BOP, a PPD < 5 mm, and no further bone loss. This was achieved in 75% of the patients and 83% of the implants in both study groups. **De Araújo Nobre et al.:** Criteria for successful treatment included the absence of SUP and BOP, a PPD ≤ 4 mm, attachment level improvement, and the absence of mobility. The HA group had a 55% success rate, whereas the CHX group had an 89% success rate; however, this difference was not statistically significant. The authors have also reported the absence of SUP for all implants post-operatively. **Friedmann et al.:** The treatment protocol resulted in healthy, non-inflamed peri-implant conditions and consistently resolved the intrabony defects.

Table 4: Summary of primary and secondary outcomes.

Outcome measure	Sánchez-Fernández et al.	Rakašević et al.	De Araújo Nobre et al.	Lopez et al.	Friedmann et al.	Soriano-Lerma et al.
Probing pocket depth (PPD) and clinical attachment loss (CAL)	Significant reduction in test group vs. control 1 at 45 and 90 days ($p < 0.01$). CAL decreased, but the change was not statistically significant in any group.	Both groups improved in PPD and CAL but without statistical differences between groups.	HA and CHX groups showed significant improvements within groups at 1 month (HA: $p = 0.031$; CHX: $p = 0.008$). Attachment level had a statistically significant change in both groups ($p < 0.05$). After 1 year, overall means of PPD and attachment level were 3.3 mm and 2.6 mm, respectively. No significant difference between groups.	Slight, statistically irrelevant difference between HA and control sides at 15 days.	Significant reduction at 12 months (3.2 ± 0.66 mm) vs. baseline (7.2 ± 1.9 mm) ($p < 0.0001$). Attachment levels were noted to be similar to those reported in literature.	Not applicable

Outcome measure	Sánchez-Fernández et al.	Rakašević et al.	De Araújo Nobre et al.	Lopez et al.	Friedmann et al.	Soriano-Lerma et al.
Bleeding on probing (BOP)	Greatest reduction in HA group at 45 and 90 days; borderline significance vs. no-product control at 90 days ($p = 0.07$).	Complete reduction in HA group at 6 months; control group 0.17 ± 0.39 ; no statistical significance.	Mean modified bleeding index scores: HA (2.2 baseline, then 1 after 1 month); CHX (1.9 baseline, then 0.7 after 1 month). After 1 year, the overall mean was 0.3.	Improvement in both HA-treated and non-HA-treated sites; no greater improvement on HA side.	Significant reduction in BOP frequency from 63% at baseline to 10% at 12 months ($p < 0.001$).	Not applicable
Marginal bone loss (MBL) / bone gain	Slight decrease in HA group (3.41 to 3.39 mm); increased loss in control groups; no statistical significance. Assessed via parallel periapical x-rays.	Significant bone gain in both groups ($p < 0.05$). Statistically greater vertical bone gain in HA group (mesial, distal, oral sites) vs. control ($p < 0.05$). Assessed via CBCT.	The post-treatment description remained similar to baseline when assessed at the 1-month follow-up. MBL not evaluated at 1-year f/u. Assessed via periapical x-rays.	Radiographic assessment of MBL was not reported.	Significant mean marginal bone gain of 1.02 ± 0.64 mm at 12 months vs. baseline (5.83 ± 2.63 mm) ($p < 0.001$). Assessed via parallel periapical x-rays. Significant defect reduction (69.1% gain of mineralized tissue).	Not applicable

Outcome measure	Sánchez-Fernández et al.	Rakašević et al.	De Araújo Nobre et al.	Lopez et al.	Friedmann et al.	Soriano-Lerma et al.
Microbiome changes	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	<p>The HA group showed a significant decrease in several bacterial genera, including <i>Streptococcus</i>, <i>Veillonella</i>, <i>Rothia</i>, <i>Granulicatella</i>, <i>Prevotella</i>, and <i>Campylobacter</i>.</p> <p>Control groups (placebo and no treatment) exhibited increases in various bacterial genera such as <i>Propionibacterium</i>, <i>Neisseria</i>, <i>Rothia</i>, <i>Pseudomonas</i>, <i>Mycoplasma</i>, <i>Atopobium</i>, and <i>Anaeroglobulus</i>, while <i>Porphyromonas</i> decreased in the no-treatment control. No significant changes were observed in Stratum 1 of the HA group.</p>

Outcome measure	Sánchez-Fernández et al.	Rakašević et al.	De Araújo Nobre et al.	Lopez et al.	Friedmann et al.	Soriano-Lerma et al.
Secondary outcomes	Pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1β, TNF-α): Significant reduction of IL-1 β in test group compared to no treatment group (p = 0.04).	ISQ: Test group showed statistically significant higher scores vs. control group at 3 and 6 months (p = 0.009 and p = 0.032).	Not secondary outcomes.	100% improvement in tartar and plaques indices but without statistical significance.	Defect reduction: Newly mineralized bone area of 27.65 \pm 18.50 mm ² (p < 0.0001, 69.1% gain of mineralized tissue).	Not secondary outcomes.
Adverse events	No adverse events were reported.	Two patients with flap dehiscence (healed uneventfully).	No adverse events were reported.	No adverse events were reported.	No premature interventions, uneventful healing.	No adverse events were reported.

3.7. Risk of bias assessment

The risk of bias was assessed for all six included studies to evaluate the quality and reliability of the evidence. RCTs were assessed using the Cochrane RoB 2 tool. Three RCTs were found to have some concerns regarding risk of bias, mainly due to retrospective registration of the trial protocol, missing data, and an unblinded (no treatment) group. One RCT was found to have a high risk of bias due to lack of a pre-registered protocol, lack of allocation concealment, missing data, and unblinding of both the patients and assessors (Table 5).

The controlled pilot study with a split-mouth design was assessed using the ROBINS-I tool and was found to have a critical risk of bias. This judgement was based on lack of randomization, the small sample size, deviations from intended interventions, unblinding of examiners, substantial amount of missing data, and absence of a pre-registered protocol (Table 6). The case series was well conducted and demonstrated methodological strengths following the assessment of the JBI checklist. However, it was determined to have a high risk of bias due to the inherent limitation of lacking a control group (Table 7).

Table 5: Risk of bias for RCTs using RoB 2.

This table shows the risk of bias for the four included RCTs using the domains of the Cochrane RoB 2 tool.

Author (Year)	RoB 2 domain 1 (Randomization)	RoB 2 domain 2 (Interventions)	RoB 2 domain 3 (Missing data)	RoB 2 domain 4 (Outcome measurement)	RoB 2 domain 5 (Reported result)	Overall risk of bias
Sánchez- Fernández et al. (2021)	Low	Some concerns (Unblinded group 2)	Some concerns (Missing data)	Low	Some concerns (Retrospective registration of trial protocol)	Some concerns
Rakašević et al. (2023)	Low	Low	Low	Low	Some concerns (Retrospective registration of trial protocol)	Some concerns
Soriano- Lerma et al. (2020)	Low	Some concerns (Unblinded group 2)	Some concerns (Missing data)	Low	Some concerns (Retrospective registration of trial protocol)	Some concerns

Author (Year)	RoB 2 domain 1 (Randomization)	RoB 2 domain 2 (Interventions)	RoB 2 domain 3 (Missing data)	RoB 2 domain 4 (Outcome measurement)	RoB 2 domain 5 (Reported result)	Overall risk of bias
De Araújo Nobre et al. (2009)	Some concerns (Lack of allocation concealment)	High (Participants were unblinded) Absence of standardized self-care protocol	High (Missing outcome data)	High (Unblinded outcome assessors)	High (Lack of a pre-specified analysis plan, protocol not registered)	High

Table 6: This table shows the risk of bias for one controlled pilot study using the ROBINS-I. (D) Domain.

Author (Year)	Study design	Tool used	Domain-specific judgments/ justification	Overall risk of bias
Lopez et al. (2017)	Controlled pilot study with a split-mouth design	ROBINS-I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D1 (Confounding): Serious risk (No randomization) ● D2 (Selection): Critical risk (Small sample size, non-random sample with unclear selection process) ● D3 (Intervention): Moderate risk (Concerns about validity of home treatment delivery method) ● D4 (Deviations): Moderate risk (Adherence to self-treatment not monitored) ● D5 (Missing data): Low risk (No reported patient dropouts) ● D6 (Measurement): Serious risk (No blinding of examiners) ● D7 (Reported result): Serious risk (No pre-registered protocol and lack of numerical/statistical data) 	Critical risk

Table 7: Risk of bias assessment of the included case series using the JBI checklist.

Author (Year)	Study design	Tool used: JBI checklist
Friedmann et al. (2024)	Case series	<p>Were there clear criteria for inclusion in the case series? Yes</p> <p>Was the condition measured in a standard, reliable way for all participants included in the case series? Yes</p> <p>Were valid methods used for identification of the condition for all participants included in the case series? Yes</p> <p>Did the case series have consecutive inclusion of participants? Unclear</p> <p>Did the case series have complete inclusion of participants? Unclear</p> <p>Was there clear reporting of the demographics of the participants in the study? Yes</p> <p>Was there clear reporting of clinical information of the participants? Yes</p> <p>Were the outcomes or follow up results of cases clearly reported? Yes</p> <p>Was there clear reporting of the presenting site(s)/clinic(s) demographic information? No</p> <p>Was statistical analysis appropriate? Yes</p> <p>Overall appraisal: Include</p>

3.8. GRADE certainty of evidence

The certainty of evidence for PPD, BOP, and MBL was assessed as the main outcomes using GRADE. The initial certainty for both PPD and BOP was rated as high because of RCTs inclusion, however, it was downgraded to moderate because of the risk of bias and imprecision, namely the small sample size. The initial certainty for MBL was high but was downgraded to very low certainty of evidence because of the risk of bias, small sample size, and inconsistency of the findings (Table 8).

Table 8: GRADE certainty of evidence summary for PPD, BOP, and MBL.

Outcome	Initial certainty	Downgrades & reasons	Final certainty
PPD	High	<p>Risk of bias: -1 (Three RCTs with some concerns, one RCT with high risk, one controlled study with critical risk, and one case series with low risk).</p> <p>Imprecision: -1 (small sample size n = 110).</p> <p>Inconsistency: Results were generally consistent.</p> <p>Indirectness: PICO was a match.</p> <p>Publication bias: No evidence was found, but not formally assessed.</p>	Moderate
BOP	High	<p>Risk of bias: -1 (Three RCTs with some concerns, one RCT with high risk, one controlled study with critical risk, and one case series with low risk).</p> <p>Imprecision: -1 (small sample size n = 110).</p> <p>Inconsistency: Results were generally consistent.</p> <p>Indirectness: PICO was a match.</p> <p>Publication bias: No evidence was found, but not formally assessed</p>	Moderate
MBL	High	<p>Risk of bias: -1 level due to high overall risk of bias.</p> <p>Inconsistency: -1 level due to inconsistent results.</p> <p>Imprecision: -1 level due to the small sample size (n = 105).</p> <p>Indirectness: PICO was a match.</p> <p>Publication bias: No evidence was found, but not formally assessed</p>	Very low

Chapter 4: Discussion

4.1. Clinical and radiographic outcomes

A consistent reduction in PPD was reported over time with statistical significance within the HA-treated groups in the studies by Sánchez-Fernández et al., Rakašević et al., De Araújo Nobre et al., and Friedmann et al. However, this was with limited intergroup superiority as only Sánchez-Fernández et al. found that outcomes were significantly better than those in the placebo group. The findings from Friedmann et al., however, were based on an intragroup analysis alone.

Additionally, there was weak evidence that the use of HA would significantly improve CAL more than other treatments. Regarding BOP, a favorable trend was observed as it was consistently reduced in all of the HA-treated groups, even though the statistical significance of these findings varied among studies.

In the studies by Rakašević et al. and Friedmann et al., a significant vertical bone gain was reported at 6 and 12 months when assessed by 3D and 2D images, respectively. Both studies treated their patients with reconstructive surgery, hence bone gain is expected.

Cerabone plus®, used in Rakašević et al., is a bovine bone substitute pre-mixed with HA. A combination of multiple treatment modalities was performed in this study, including titanium brushes, photodynamic therapy, implantoplasty of exposed threads, post-operative antibiotics, and CHX use. While combining these approaches might be beneficial for the patients suffering from the disease, it makes isolating the true effects of HA challenging.

In the case series by Friedmann et al., HyaDENT BG® was applied to the implant and defect wall surfaces as well as the ribose cross-linked collagen matrix, which covered the defects without the addition of bone substitutes. Despite the positive bone gain outcome, the reconstructive treatment resulted in a statistically significant soft tissue dehiscence. This recession should be viewed as a potential consequence of the overall treatment approach and the pre-operative reported stage of bone loss rather than a specific result of the HA component.

In the included non-surgical treatment studies, there was stability in MBL, but no evidence of bone gain. Both Sánchez-Fernández et al. and De Araújo Nobre et al. assessed their findings using periapical x-rays. However, the former study reported MBL in millimeters up to a 90-day follow-up, whereas the latter's description of MBL was less accurate as it would not detect small changes by reporting its level according to the implant thirds, and after a short follow-up of only one month. Radiographic assessment of MBL was not included among the studied descriptive outcomes in Lopez et al., although it is a crucial component in peri-implantitis.

4.2. Biological and microbiological effects

IL-1 and TNF, pro-inflammatory cytokines, are key markers of destructive periodontal disease. They stimulate a cascade of events that amplify the inflammatory response leading to bone and attachment loss (Graves & Cochran, 2003). Levels of IL-1 β are found to be elevated in the gingival crevicular fluid of patients with chronic periodontitis compared to healthy individuals, with particularly high levels in older patients. Increased TNF is linked to chronic periodontitis as well, and suppressing both factors may down-regulate the severity of the periodontal disease. A significant reduction in IL-1 β levels was achieved with non-surgical treatment (Neurath & Kesting, 2024).

Sánchez-Fernández et al. found that HA demonstrated a strong anti-inflammatory effect, as levels of IL-1 β were significantly reduced in patients with PPD \geq 5 mm in the test group ($p = 0.04$) when compared to the no-treatment group. However, De Araújo Nobre et al. suggested that HA is more suitable for cases with a PPD up to 5 mm as they reported only one successful treatment in a 6 mm pocket, in addition to the other successful treatments of \leq 5 mm pockets against their set success criteria.

Soriano-Lerma et al. described three groups of bacteria. HA did not have an effect on the stratum 1 group, which consisted of environmental bacteria that came from an exogenous source, such as water, including *Ralstonia* and *Sphingomonas*. The effect of HA was significant in decreasing stratum 2, the group of bacteria interpreted as early colonizers, such as *Streptococcus*, *Veillonella*, *Neisseria*, and *Rothia*, which are part of plaque biofilm.

The effect of HA on stratum 3, described as the late colonizers, was mild on *Prevotella* and *Campylobacter*, which have a strong link to periodontitis and peri-implantitis, but it was found to lower the diversity in this group.

The authors concluded that peri-implantitis can be caused by either opportunistic non-oral bacteria or common oral bacteria. Their findings also suggest that HA is more beneficial in the early stages of peri-implantitis, as it effectively disrupts the maturation to late-stage bacterial colonies, or that it could be used as a preventive measure to maintain implant health.

4.3. Limitations

Among the included studies, there was variability in the diagnostic and success criteria, with inconsistent thresholds for PPD and MBL. Additionally, SUP is one of the recognized clinical signs of peri-implantitis, however, this measure was not consistently reported or quantified as a finding across the included studies. There was significant heterogeneity across the studies' designs, particularly the highly variable use of HA. This was evident in the differences in its specific formulation, delivery methods, and directions for use. This lack of standardization is a key difference from agents like CHX, which have established clinical regimens and are, in most cases, prescribed by clinicians in a more uniform manner.

The studies also varied in the types of controls, follow-up durations, and the fundamental implementation of surgical reconstruction. Due to this wide variation and the limited number of studies, it presents a significant challenge to draw firm conclusions and provide clear clinical directions. Therefore, a meta-analysis was not performed as it would have resulted in an unreliable and underpowered summary.

One of the factors that downgraded the certainty of evidence for MBL to very low was the inconsistency of results. The two studies that used surgical approaches reported a significant improvement in bone gain, while the other two studies that utilized the non-surgical approach and analyzed MBL showed no significant changes. Besides other factors, the intervention approach appears to be directly related to this heterogeneity in outcomes. This suggests that the efficacy of HA in treating bone loss may be highly dependent on surgical integration potentially being a prerequisite for achieving a therapeutic effect with many of the currently available HA products for intraoral use.

The small sample size of the included studies is a limitation of the precision and certainty of the evidence presented in this review. It is important to recognize that this is an expected finding, given the complexity of treating peri-implantitis, especially with the use of HA as a relatively rare and unpopular intervention.

4.4. Comparison with existing literature

Non-surgical treatment of peri-implantitis is expected to improve clinical outcomes by 20%-50% in BOP and achieve a ≤ 1 mm reduction in PPD; however, it is unlikely to resolve advanced cases (Renvert et al., 2019). In a randomized clinical trial that assessed the efficacy of adjunctive systemic antibiotics in the treatment of peri-implantitis, all patients were treated with non-surgical therapy and were instructed to use CHX twice a day for four weeks. The test group received a combined amoxicillin and metronidazole regimens. However, this did not have a statistical significance in reducing PPD as the primary measured outcome. Moreover, both groups did not show improvement in BOP (Polymeri et al., 2022).

In a review evaluating bone regeneration in peri-implantitis treatments, it was reported that vertical bone gain is usually limited and not as predictable as the improvement in clinical signs including BOP and PPD. Additionally, the amount of bone fill is highly dependent on the defect morphology, with four-wall defects having a better prognosis. Moreover, initial deeper vertical defects were found to have a significantly greater radiographic defect fill after a one year of follow-up compared to shallower ones (Noelken & Al-Nawas, 2023).

In a systematic review and meta-analysis assessing peri-implant tissue changes, reconstructive surgery was associated with better outcomes when compared to non-reconstructive surgeries. They reported a mean bone gain by 1.95 mm (95% CI [0.05; 3.86], $p = .044$) and a reduction of PPD by 1.27 mm (95% CI [-1.96; -0.60], $p < .001$) (Sanz-Martín et al., 2021).

Another systematic review and meta-analysis assessing peri-implant osseous defects, found similar positive results for bone gain. Reconstructive surgical techniques in the treatment of peri-implantitis had better outcomes than open flap debridement in terms of bone refill with a mean gain of 1.01 mm (95% CI: 0.55–1.46; $p = .0001$). However, no significant differences were found between the approaches in improving BOP and PPD (Risolo et al., 2023).

Many findings of the study by Soriano-Lerma et al. are supported by a meta-analysis of the microbiota associated with peri-implantitis (Carvalho É et al., 2023), which associates the disease with specific pathogens, including *P. gingivalis*, *T. forsythia*, *T. denticola*, *F. nucleatum*, and *P. intermedia*, all of which were found to fall within the third stratum. Furthermore, viruses such as human herpesvirus 4, Epstein–Barr 1, and cytomegalovirus 2 were detected in peri-implantitis sites (Ting et al., 2018).

Still, a single, universal microbial profile for peri-implantitis has yet to be agreed upon, but in essence there is general consensus that peri-implantitis sites are not uniform in their bacterial composition (Chun Giok & Menon, 2023).

Literature reports no strong evidence to suggest the most effective treatment intervention for peri-implantitis. The adjunctive use of CHX in non-surgical peri-implantitis therapy was not found to have a significant improvement in key clinical parameters, including PPD, BOP, and CAL. Consequently, its efficacy is considered limited (Liu et al., 2020; Ye et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2021).

In a comprehensive overview of systematic reviews on peri-implantitis, it was found to likely occur after 5 years of loading the implant. Patients with a history of periodontitis, uncontrolled diabetes, cardiovascular disease, or smoking are at greater risk of developing the condition. Combining surgical and non-surgical treatments can lead to successful outcomes without identifying a single most effective one. Additionally, any non-surgical treatment combined with another intervention is more effective than debridement alone (Ting et al., 2018).

4.5. Future research

The current evidence for the use of HA to treat peri-implantitis is promising but limited by significant heterogeneity across studies. To establish HA's efficacy, future research should focus on standardization and well-designed clinical trials. Standardized protocols, long-term follow-up, and larger sample sizes are necessary to provide definitive evidence. Studies should also explore whether the concentration of HA influences clinical outcomes.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

Taking into account the high heterogeneity in protocols and HA formulations, the findings showed promising clinical outcomes, though with significant limitations such as small sample sizes and a high risk of bias. The current evidence is insufficient to favor clinical superiority over other adjunctive treatments.

Adjunctive HA appears to be effective in improving clinical parameters: BOP and PPD with a moderate certainty of evidence. A significant marginal bone gain was observed exclusively when HA was used in conjunction with reconstructive surgical procedures; however, the overall certainty of evidence remains very low.

Furthermore, HA was found to be beneficial in decreasing the levels of early colonizer bacteria, disrupting the maturation of late-stage bacteria, and showing a potent anti-inflammatory effect by reducing the levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 β . The findings of this review suggest that HA may have its most beneficial effect when used in the early stages of peri-implantitis.

Chapter 6: References

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